

Role of Digitalization in Exposing PMC Bank Scam- A Case Study

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Abstract

The digitalization has been playing a extensive role in all the sector of the economy, and the banking sector is not an exception to it. The Indian banking sector, which plays an important role in furthering financial inclusion and mainly concerned with providing better services to the customer along with an opportunity to gain more the near future. The Indian Banking sectors accomplish tremendous growth in recent years because of the digitalization of banking. Digitalization has various features one of the authentic important features is transparency; it helps to identify the frauds in all the different functions of the bank.

This paper has the objective of explaining the scam that has happened recently; it also tries to find out the reasons for the PMC bank scam and to avoid any activity that could lead to such a bank scam. This study would also help to know the prevention measure that could take it in the future.

Keywords: proper understanding, preventive measure, in-depth

Introduction Digitalization

Digitalization is a modifying the data into digital form. Digitalization means the approval of technology. But these two words are being used interchangeably.

In other words: storing the file in electronic format, converting the media into electronic form.

Role of Digitalization in the Banking Industry

The key benefits of digitalization in banking is very much improving with more business efficiency, colossal cost savings, accurate and reliable performance, and fast internal and external processes. The digitalization has been examined by 47% bankers as a medium for the betterment of customer relationships, while 44% of bankers feel this channel would help them stay ahead of the competition. The study of digitalization in banking further found 32% of believing digital banking helps in customer procurement, while for 16%, this channel would lead to cost-saving.

Digitalization is not an option for the banking industry; it is imminent because every industry is digitalize, and the banking sector is no exception. Mobile banking is more than increasing online banking. Banks are not just a part of our lives but have a special place in our lives; the day will not end without any single financial transaction. The banks always try to adopt the latest technology to enhance the customer experience.

Objectives of this Paper

1. To study the scam in Punjab and Maharashtra co-operative bank ltd
2. To analysis the scam
3. To provide suggestions for prevention of such scam

Sources of Information

Secondary data was collected published, and unpublished work was studied to collect information released by the government of India onrelated websites.

Profile of Punjab and Maharashtra Co-Operative Bank Limited

It is a multi-state co-operative bank, which is established on February 13, 1984, this bank has total deposits of about Rs 11,617.34 crores. It has 137 branches spread over six states of India, and 100 office are in Maharashtra. It is supervise by the Reserve Bank of India and registered under the Co-operative Societies Act.

This bank is one of the profitable co-operative banks in India and had earned a total income of Rs 1,297 crores (US\$188 million) and profits of Rs 99.69 crores (US\$14 million) in the financial year 2019.

Vision and Mission

1. To develop as a active, dynamic, most preferred premier co-operative bank, committed to excellence in serving the customer, and enhance stakeholder's value through concern, care, and competence.
2. Punjab and Maharashtra Co-operative bank is a multi-state urban co-operative bank with its area of operation in the states of karnataka, Goa, Delhi, Gujarat, Andra Pradesh, and Madya Pradesh.
3. The humble beginning of the bank is done in a small room at Sino On February 13, 1983, single branch bank. In a span 35 years. The bank has a deep network of 137 branches across six states.
4. The bank stands among the top 10 co-operative banks of the country.

Data on the Scam of Pmc Bank LTD

The customers of PMC Bank were shocked to hear a message from the bank that said it had been put under directions by the RBI for six months.

An analysis in Money control said when RBI puts a bank under its directions; it means that it is taking over the bank's operations. The Management is taken over, and the board is dissolved. It is because the regulator is not satisfied with the bank's functioning, and steps are taken to safeguard the interest of borrowers.

In PMC Bank's case, RBI found some irregularities in lending loans under-reporting of non-performing assets or higher than permitted exposure to the same group accounts, which is why it has led RBI to take the step. The bank's customers demanded explanations from the bank, and the police had to interfere with maintain order.

In some PMC branches, officials were absent.

ATMs are shut, and security guards are seeing putting up an apology from the bank's MD. Customers are devastated as they could withdraw only up to Rs 1,000 from the bank.

The Published Details

The details as follows report in ET claimed, the number of irregularities came as a shock as much as 73% of PMC's 88 billion rupee loan book or almost \$920 million – was given to just one borrower group namely Housing Development and Infrastructure Ltd., a Mumbai-based shantytown

developer that’s currently facing bankruptcy proceedings said a letter written by PMC bank’s now-suspended managing director to the RBI. The executive had told BloombergQuint that about a third of the bank’s loans are given to HDIL.

According to ET, it is said that the size of the reported loans given is far in excess of the bank’s capital. This goes beyond a failure of oversight and would require top-level complicity.

PMC’s annual report shows it is to be a profitable lender with a capital adequacy ratio higher than the 12% minimum requirements and a bad-loan ratio of under 4%—almost acceptable by the current standards of India’s banking industry.

The Economic Offences Wing of Mumbai Police said in court last week that PMC replaced 44 loan accounts of the HDIL group with over 21,000 fictitious loan accounts, thereby hiding defaults by the group. It is imperative to know about HDIL, about this case—is that HDIL is in bankruptcy court after failing to repay debt.

The National Company Law Tribunal confirmed insolvency proceedings against the Mumbai-based builder HDIL following an appeal filed by Bank of India under Section 7 of the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code. The police claimed the loans from PMC bank are not recorded in the core banking system. Instead, they are only entries in the master indent (or the details of loan accounts) submitted to the RBI for inspection.

The police officials also said that the board of directors and executives, including MD Joy Thomas, fully aware of this. Joy Thomas is arrested last Friday. The testimony also said the Wadhwas, who owns and runs HDIL, played active roles in the fraud and demanded custodial interrogation was to trace the operations carried out with the funds borrowed from the bank.

According to reports in BloombergQuint, the Enforcement Directorate is also conducting inquiries on PMC under the Prevention of Money Laundering Act.

The Economic Offences Wing seized property worth 500 crores that belong to certain entities involved in the supposed 4,355.43 crore PMC scam.

A report in Mint said that, with this week’s move, the total amount of seizures is estimated at approximately Rs 4,000 crore.

HDIL promoters Rakesh Wadhwa and his son Sarang Wadhwa are arrested on charges of closed involvement in the fraud. It has also come to light that the bank did not report its exposure to HDIL for 6-7 years.

Following these, PMC Bank appointed Grant Thornton, as suggested by the police, to conduct a forensic investigation into the allegations made by ex-MD Joy Thomas. Thomas confessed crores to the Reserve Bank that PMC’s exposure to the bankrupt HDIL goes past 6,500 crores rupees—four times the regulatory cap, or 73% of its assets of 8,88 crores!

According to an analysis in Mint, it is found out that the crisis at PMC Bank is a sign of a Compatriot plaguing around 1,500 co-operative banks in the country. Typically these banks are loosely monitored as they come under the dual regulation of both the state government and RBI. While the central bank is responsible for the supervision, other activities like bank management are monitored by the Register of Co-operative Societies.

Media reports showed that 5-10% of total deposits are withdrawn daily basis since 19 September. Such withdrawals could be as high as 29% of total deposits. As of 31 March, the bank’s total deposits stood at 11,617 crore rupees. More than 60% of the co-operative bank’s customer had small deposits of around Rs 10,000 each in the bank.

The large withdrawals came to light after some of the large depositors got a serpent of a whistleblower’s complaint to the regulator. Within a short time, the bank’s suspended MD and CEO Joy Thomas wrote a confession letter to RBI admitting that the actual exposure to HDIL was over Rs 6,500 crores. The annual report audited by Lakdawala and Company shows that the Bank had reported

a net profit of 99.69crores compared to 100.90crores a year ago. Capital adequacy of the bank was at 12.62%, and net non-performing loans stood at 2.19%. Despite this, the regulator and the bank's auditors seemed to have no suspicion of the fact that the Wadhwa group's exposure, which stood at approximately 500crore till 2006-07, had swelled out to 6,500crores. As recently as August 2018, PMC Bank had played out a loan of 96.5crores to HDIL - to settle its dues with Bank of India and therefore stop it from causing insolvency proceedings. Continuing by the investigations by the ED and Mumbai Police, the Institute of Chartered Accountants of India has decided to inquire about Lakdawala & Co.

It is seen that there are old connections between PMC Bank and the Wadhwa. That relationship was back in the 1980s. In 1986, just two years after it began operations, PMC Bank is the edge of financial collapse. Rajesh Kumar Wadhwa, a former director of Land Development Corp and many other companies run by the Dewan family (who would become a promoter of HDIL), put Rs 13lakhs into the bank that budgetary. Mint reporting that the family also kept a large number of deposits for the improvement of the bank. At another time, he filled almost a 100crores to help the bank to come over a liquidity crunch.

The change began when the group started facing a liquidity crunch in 2012. One of the reasons is the cancellation of HDIL's slum rehabilitation project near Mumbai airport. The cancellation affected the group defaulting on dues to all banks, which stopped the Wadhwas from raising fresh capital or loans, and consequently, their projects are obstructed.

Thomas's letter to the RBI said that the loans outstanding are huge, and if these are classified as non-performing assets, it would have affected the profitability of the bank, and the bank would have faced regulatory action from RBI this would have created a reputation risk for the bank. As the HDIL group had a good record of cleaning their dues with convinced delays, we continued to report all the accounts as standard accounts.

Present Situation

Many investors are asking for government interference.

The Eden Garden Cooperative Housing Society in Mumbai's Oshiwara, which is home to 29 families, cannot access the Rs 24lakh it has in PMC Bank. They told Bloomberg that their entire amount had been locked up now. They have no money. They had kept fixed deposits, sinking funds, maintenance fees, and other savings in PMC Bank. They have no idea how they are going to manage in this situation. There's no money to pay for utilities like electricity bill, water bill, fees of the watchman, gardener, and others. Guru Nanak School in Mumbai, Reena Rishigan, principal of the school, told Mint the school and its teachers have savings accounts with PMC Bank. She told that the school is not able to pay their monthly salaries and other bills amounting to nearly 80,000 rupees in the current month.

At a meeting of PMC Bank depositors, one person who has almost no hopes said that the government can easily infuse 2,000crores and restart the bank. It can seize the property of HDIL and help reopen the bank. The bank has 11,000crores worth of deposits and has lent only 4,000crore to HDIL.

Bombay High Court lawyer Vinod Sampat told that legally, there's no way for the housing societies or the individual depositors to get back their money. He explained that this is a systematic failure that occurred because of lack of due diligence on the part of government authorities like officials from RBI, PMC Bank, auditors, among others. For the housing societies and individual account holders, this is going to only wait and watch the situation. Chances of getting back their entire money is pretty less. Some statements from the RBI have put in hope for such depositors. RBI Governor Shaktikant Das told, The Reserve Bank of India would not allow a cooperative Bank to collapse while answering to questions regarding the PMC bank scam.

Analysis of Pmc Bank Scam

What appears in the PMC bank’s case?

RBI has not yet given any exact reason for delivering guidance, but it is announced that the regulator found irregularities in contribution under-reporting of non-performing assets or higher than permitted disclosure to the same company accounts. An investigation is presently ongoing.

What are the Restrictions on Customers?

Customers can withdraw only up to Rs 1000 from the bank, irrespective of the types of accounts. They can restate existing term deposits on capability. In case of an emergency consumption like hospitalization etc. the RBI may allow an omission on a case-by-case basis.

Restriction on a Bank?

1. The bank cannot accept fresh deposits or allotment new loans without previous approval from RBI.
2. ATMs have been taken off the outlay network.
3. Online banking has been stopped.

The Present Health of PMC bank?

1. PMC Bank’s net profit of 2019 at Rs 99.69 crores.
2. Bank’s total deposits stood at Rs 11,617 crores as of March 2019.
3. Bank’s total loans and advances stood at Rs 8,383 crores.
4. Gross NPV ratio as of March 2019 stood at Rs 3.76%
5. It employs 1,814 people as of 31 March 2019.

What is the Future of PMC Bank?

After six months, RBI will take a call on whether to relax some restrictions or extend the duration. If the distinction found can be corrected over time, the bank’s action will be re-evaluated (even before six months)

It may lead to complete termination of the bank. In such a scenario, the bank’s arrangement with the Deposit Insurance and Credit Guarantee Corporation (DICGC) will kick in. Under this, customers will be eligible to claim up to Rs 1 lakh of their deposits with the bank.

RBI Imposes Restrictions on PMC Bank

The restrictions were issues on money resignation, circulation of loans, and opening of fixed deposits accounts. The RBI had also set a withdrawal limit of Rs 1000 as a result of which depositors were not adequate to withdraw more than Rs 1000 from their savings, current or any other account in the PMC bank.

RBI Directions: Key Highlights

- It issues or renews loans and advances or open fixed deposits account for the next six months.
- It is restricted from making any step of investment and obtains recent deposits without advance endorsement from the RBI.
- It has been restricted from acquiring any liability, including borrowing of funds or contributes or even agreeing to disburse any payment without prior written approval from RBI.
- Now the withdrawal limit has been enlarged to Rs 10,000 for the six months.

Conclusion

PMC is a bank with several positives that work in its favor: a multi-state network of 137 perfectly functional branches with modest computer operating systems. An incredible client base of depositors and account holders, a wide network of ATM centers and the capacity to offer services 24*7.

If the RBI takes stock of these factors methodically, gets an evaluation made, and pitched the case of the Bank in professional terms, even private bank’s may show an interest in taking it over.

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